

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF SAND ADHESION TO SAND-COATED GFRP BARS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports a study intended to assess the adhesion of sand coating to sand-coated GFRP reinforcing bars and thereby determine whether this may affect the bond performance of such bars. A simple test method and apparatus is demonstrated that can be used to assess adhesion of sand coating to FRP bars. Sand adhesion test results are compared with ASTM D7913 pull-off tests. It was confirmed that, for the GFRP bars considered, the adhesion of the sand coating was superior to the bond capacity of the bar, although not by as great a margin as one may expect.

KEYWORDS

adhesion; bond behavior; prism tension test; pull-out test; sand-coated FRP bars

INTRODUCTION

GFRP reinforcing bars are manufactured with a variety surface deformations – indentations (machined ribs), sand coating, and helical wrapping, among others – in order to provide mechanical bond to the concrete in which the bars are embedded. Most of these surface treatments differ significantly from the surface deformations of conventional steel reinforcing bars.

Predictions for bond, and related cracking behaviour, of GFRP-reinforced concrete members are generally based on formulations similar to those used conventional steel-reinforced concrete. To account for the differences of bond between GFRP bars, a bond-dependent coefficient, k_b , is adopted to measure relative bar performance. In other words, k_b is a factor that allows the designer to treat other materials or bar geometries in essentially the same manner as conventional deformed steel bars.

Since bond behaviour models for conventional steel bars are relatively well-known and considered to be adequate, steel bars conforming to the geometry requirements of ASTM A615 have $k_b = 1.0$. For other bar types, a factor $1/k_b$ is applied in order to normalize bond properties to those of deformed steel bars. That is, when FRP exhibits bond behaviour similar that to deformed steel bars, $k_b = 1.0$; for FRP bars having bond behaviour inferior to steel bars, k_b is greater than 1.0; and for FRP reinforcement presenting bond performance superior to steel, k_b is less than 1.0.

Many values of k_b are reported in literature in an attempt to encompass the different surface configurations of GFRP bars available, although there is no consensus. It is reported that k_b is influenced by factors such as bar type, bar diameter, concrete strength, and service stress level in the reinforcement (McCallum and Newhook, 2012; Noel and Soudki, 2013). Across the literature, reported values of k_b range from about 0.6 to 1.8 (a large dataset of bond tests is presented by Silva 2023). In the absence of test data, $k_b = 1.4$ is recommended for design (ACI 440.1-15) whereas Shield et al. (2019) recommend $k_b = 1.2$ for sand-coated GFRP bars and $k_b = 1.4$ otherwise. One consistent finding across the literature is that sand-coated GFRP bars exhibit improved bond characteristics over other deformation types (Shield et al. 2019; Silva 2023). Additionally, the value of k_b reported for

sand-coated GFRP bars are often less than 1.0, indicating that sand-coated GFRP bars can exhibit better bond properties than conventional steel reinforcing bars.

Shifting to the GFRP bar geometry itself, surface deformations of GFRP bars usually present lower shear strength than the rolled-in surface ribs or lugs of steel bars. The shear capacity at the concrete-resin (i.e., concrete-GFRP bar) and resin-fiber interfaces (i.e., internal to the bar) in a bond failure are influenced by the deformation geometry of the GFRP bars (Al-Zahrani et al. 1999; Al-Mahmoud et al. 2007). In some older GFRP bars – especially those having post-applied wrapped deformations, the deformations have been observed to shear off (e.g. Moon et al. 2008). Similar to a GFRP lug, the sand coating on a sand-coated can be ‘sheared off’ the bar. The sand is typically broadcast onto the bar as it is pultruded and is therefore ‘embedded’ into the vinyl ester resin matrix prior to cure. There is no standard method to quantify the resulting shear capacity (adhesion) of the sand and underlying bar.

This paper reports a pilot experimental study intended to assess the adhesion of the sand coating to the GFRP bar and thereby determine whether this may affect the bond performance of the bar.

Motivation for study

In a recent study (Silva 2023), apparently contradictory results were observed for the bond capacity of sand-coated GFRP bars determined using ASTM D7913 pull-out tests and using tension tests of long single bars embedded in a concrete prism (Silva et al. 2023). ASTM D7913, which tests a short 5 bar diameter ($5d_b$) bonded region, results in very high bond stress results which are believed to capture the peak bond stress capacity of a bar. Long prism tests (those reported by Silva use a specimen that is $150d_b$ long) result in average bond stress values over the bar length between resulting cracks and are believed to be more representative of what may be obtained in flexural members.

Bond test results for #4 (12.7 mm nominal diameter) and #5 (15.9 mm) bars tested by Silva (2023) are given in Table 1. All bars (ASTM D7913 and prism tests) were embedded in the same batch of concrete having $f_c' = 37.8$ MPa. In this test program, the prism test results indicated the largely expected result that the sand-coated GFRP bars perform better than ribbed GFRP and conventional ribbed steel bars. Based on this test series, a value of $k_b = 0.66$ is predicted. However, the ASTM D7913 results for the same bars in the same concrete indicate an opposing trend. In this case, the value $k_b = 2.24$ was determined for the #4 sand-coated bars. This latter results was surprising and contradicted not only the prism test results, but common wisdom that sand-coated bars exhibit improved bond.

Table 1: Summary of bond test results (Silva 2023)

bar type	#4 ASTM A 615 steel	#4 ribbed GFRP	#4 sand-coated GFRP	#5 sand-coated GFRP
measured diameter, d_b	12.5 mm	13.8 mm	13.2 mm	17.5 mm
measured area of bar, A	119 mm ²	146 mm ²	122 mm ²	219 mm ²
modulus, E	200 GPa	60.3 GPa	46.9 GPa	24.4 GPa
ultimate strength, f_{tu}	$f_y = 400$ MPa	962 MPa	927 MPa	739 MPa
τ_{max} per ASTM D7913	16.45 MPa (0.11)	12.51 MPa (0.18)	7.33 MPa (0.39)	10.78 MPa (0.16)
τ_{max} per prism test	7.00 MPa	6.12 MPa	10.58 MPa	not tested
COV (in parentheses) for ASTM D7913 tests reported based on sample size of 10 in each case.				

SAND ADHESION TEST

One hypothesis for the observed behaviour was that for sand-coated bars, a failure mode involving shearing the sand coating from the bars is possible. Typically, the bond of the sand-coating to the bar is assumed to be adequate; although if it were not, the contradictory results observed may arise: the sand-coated bar may behave very well in a long prism test but poorly in a pull-out test having a short

embedment and higher bond stresses. This paper reports a bespoke experimental study intended to assess the adhesion of the sand coating to the GFRP bar and thereby determine whether this may affect the bond performance of the bar.

Test Specimens and Procedure

Five short lengths of the subject #4 and #5 sand-coated GFRP bars were tested (Figure 1a). The bars are cut longer than 50 mm. Measured bar properties are given in Table 1.

Two 50 mm long hollow steel cylinders were fabricated (Figures 1b and 1c). The inside diameter, d , is about 4 mm larger than the measured diameter of the finished bar to be tested ($d_b = 13.2$ and 17.5 mm for #4 and #5 bars, respectively). A collar having a reduced inside diameter (aperture) $D = 11.9$ mm and 16.8 mm for the #4 and #5 bars, respectively, corresponding to the diameter of the bar without sand, is provided at midheight of the cylinder. The length of the collar is $b = 3.2$ and 4.5 mm for #4 and #5 bars, respectively, approximately one quarter the bar diameter. The upper 25 mm of the cylinder has a centering apparatus, allowing the bar to be installed without eccentricity relative to the collar (Figure 1). It should be noted that the test apparatus must be custom made for each bar type used since outer dimensions of sand-coated bars can vary substantially.

Bars were placed vertically in the steel cylinder and the assembly was positioned in a servo hydraulic testing machine (Figure 1d). The bar was pushed into the cylinder at a rate of 1 mm/s. The bar is forced through the collar aperture which ‘shears off’ the sand coating. Displacement and load were recording from the tests. At 25 mm displacement, the bar has been fully pushed through the cylinder assembly and its end begins to bear on the test machine: the load increases signifying the end of the test.

The test is affected by friction and the accumulation of the removed sand surface around the aperture. The force required to shear the sand from the perimeter of the bars is given in terms of *force per mm circumference of the bar* and is determined at a displacement b , corresponding to the bar first entirely engaging the aperture collar:

$$p_{sand} = P_b/b \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where P_b is the applied load at displacement b , and b is the length of the aperture.

A comparison is made with the ASTM D7913 test results. The bond stress determined in the ASTM D7913 test is assumed to be acting uniformly over the $5d_b$ embedment length. From this, the force acting on a portion of the bar perimeter is:

$$p_{D7913} = P_{max}/5d_b = \tau_{max}\pi d_b \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where $\tau_{max} = P_{max}/5\pi d_b^2$ is the shear stress from the ASTM D7913 test ($5d_b$ is the length of bar embedment and πd_b is the bar circumference). In Eq. 2, by convention, d_b is based on the nominal bar diameter, 12.7 mm and 15.9 mm for #4 and #5 bars, respectively.

a) #4 and #5 sand-coated bars tested

b) isometric drawing of test apparatus

c) top and bottom of #4 test apparatus

d) #5 bar being tested – bar is pushed into steel cylinder, shearing off sand coating

Figure 1: Test specimens and apparatus.

SAND ADHESION TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five samples of each of the #4 and #5 sand-coated GFRP bars were tested to determine the force required to shear the sand from bar surface. The results are presented in terms of displacement versus applied load in Figure 2 and individual results are summarised in Table 2.

a) #4 bars

b) #5 bars

Figure 2: Applied load versus displacement results for sand adhesion tests

Table 2: Results from sand adhesion tests.

bars	d_b	b	sample	P_b	$p_{sand} = P_b/b$	τ_{max}	p_{D7913} $= \tau_{max}\pi d_b$
	mm	mm		N	N/mm		MPa
#4	13.2	3.2	1	2313	723		
			2	3491	1091		
			3	3341	1044		
			4	3125	977		
			5	3512	1098		
			average		986	7.33	292
			COV		0.157	0.39	
#5	17.5	4.5	1	2995	666		
			2	2470	549		
			3	2888	642		
			4	3678	817		
			5	3863	858		
			average		706	10.78	538
			COV		0.182	0.16	

It is seen in Figure 2 that the applied force varies considerably during the test although does not fall below the force at which the entire aperture is engaged at displacement b . The variation and continued gradual increase in load is associated with friction and the accumulation of removed sand in the upper chamber of the test apparatus.

For both bar types tested, the force required to shear the sand from the bar exceeded that seen in the ASTM D7913 tests. Thus we conclude that sand adhesion was unlikely to be a factor contributing to the low bond stress results observed for these bars in the ASTM D7913 tests.

However, the results for the #5 bars indicate some likelihood that sand adhesion may affect pull-out results. Considering the variation inherent in both tests (and assuming a Gaussian distribution of results), the probability that $p_{D7913} > p_{sand}$ – the condition in which sand adhesion affects the ASTM D7913 pull-out test – is 14% for the #5 bars tested. The same probability of sand adhesion failure for the #4 bars is negligible.

The motivation for this study was poor observed bond strength results for sand-coated GFRP bars (Table 1). Had either of these bars achieved parity (i.e. $k_b = 1$) with the #4 steel bars tested ($\tau_{max} = 16.45$ MPa), the value of p_{D7913} increases to 656 N/mm and 822 N/mm for the #4 and #5 bars, respectively. This would indicate a possible sand adhesion failure for at least the #5 bars tested.

CONCLUSIONS

It was confirmed that, for the sand-coated GFRP bars considered, the adhesion of the sand coating to the bar was superior to the bond capacity of the bar, although not by as great a margin as one may expect. While sand-coated bars are usually observed to behave better than comparable deformed bars, the preliminary results presented here suggest that sand adhesion to the bars could control bond strength in some cases. Ultimately, however, the reasons for the apparently low bond stress results for the bars tested is not deemed to be adhesion failure of the sand in this instance.

This paper reported a pilot study of a simple test method and apparatus that can be used to assess adhesion of sand coating to FRP bars and may be adapted to consider the shear capacity of lugs on other types of FRP bars. The results reported are limited to the bars tested.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.